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D7.2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

30/11/2024

Authors:

Quentin Morel (TEN)

Pauline Bonino (TEN)

Esperanza Sedano Varo (CID)

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
LOM	Lomartov
POLITO	Politecnico di Torino
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SSB	Solid-state batteries
OS	Open Science
M1-M12	Month 1 – Month 12
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
SET plan	Strategic Energy Technology Plan
AB	Advisory Board
CID	CIDETEC

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document traces the strategy for the dissemination and communication activities of the SOLVE project. It aims to support the project partners in carrying out appropriate and effective communication activities and ensuring they are conducted in accordance with requirements detailed in the Grant Agreement. This document should be used as a handbook to be accessed frequently by partners to understand the external communication procedures for the project.

It will thus present the following points:

- It describes the overall external communication objectives for SOLVE and the project target audiences and potential key messages.
- It lists and describes the key external communication tools, including visual identity, project website and social media accounts.
- It describes the key external communication activities, including publications, press releases, the link with other EU policies and EU projects as well as the external publications.
- It describes what should be the partners' involvement in the project communication through their social media & website, participation to events, proposals for publications.
- It presents how the project communication and dissemination will be monitored and evaluated through "Key Performance Indicators" (KPIs) and how each partner should report on its communication activities.

This document is therefore a communication plan which allows the implementation of the strategy as defined in the application form.

1. THE COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

1.1. REMINDER OF THE PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Solid-state batteries (SSB) offer a promising opportunity for the EU to become an early player and enhance its position in the global battery market.

Supported by a consortium comprised of key industry and academic players in the battery field, SOLVE aims to capitalize on the extensive R&D base and contribute to the scaling-up efforts required for Gen4b mass production.

To this end, SOLVE will address the most significant barriers hindering sector growth by demonstrating innovations across the main stages of the value chain, optimizing active and inactive materials, and associated processing techniques under industrially relevant conditions (TRL \geq 6).

This entire process will be reinforced by the implementation of novel digital tools and models to support and accelerate the cell design process., as well as the incorporation of imperative sustainability criteria to promote efficient resource utilization through eco-design principles and the development of innovative recycling processes.

1.2. REMINDER OF THE COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION OBJECTIVES

The dissemination, use and valorization of the project results make a crucial contribution in the achievement of the expected outcomes and impacts. It will include activities to raise awareness about how the use of R&I European funds contributes to address societal challenges, the importance of R&D in supporting the decarbonization of the mobility sector and the need to strengthen the relationships between science, industry and the society.

Specific objectives:

- **Community building (M1-M12):** Generation of a community of interested stakeholders. During this phase, messages will focus on informing and generating awareness on the basics: SOLVE's objectives, expected results and impacts, introduction to consortium members, etc.
- **R&D diffusion and cooperation (M12-M36):** As the results of the project emerge, mainly from the second year onwards, dissemination activities will be focus on both the one-way transfer of project's data and outputs to targeted stakeholders, as well as in activities such as the attendance to events and conferences that enable the active feedback and participation of stakeholders in the research lifecycle. On their end, communication activities to the general public will incorporate information on the main project advancements in easy-to-understand language for non-expert audiences.
- **Exploitation enablement (M24-M48):** Towards the end of the project, dissemination activities will be oriented to support the actual exploitation of project results, reinforcing the visibility and transfer of knowledge to end users, mainly industry, sectoral associations and policymakers.

1.3. COMMUNICATION TARGET

Target audiences: Interests, benefits and key messages for project's outcomes

Universities and research centers: Research institutions will greatly benefit from the project's OS approach, which will enable a wider replication of advances in the SSB technology, multiplying its potential impact, as well as the specific cooperation and dissemination activities targeted to the scientific community. **Key messages** will emphasize collaboration opportunities to contribute to R&I in SSBs, targeting strong players outside the consortium such as CNRS, CIC Energigune, VTT, TNO, AIT, MEET, FZJ, WMG, IMN, Blue Lab and others.

Active material providers and processors: Material and component suppliers and producers will benefit from cell component's advancements made within the project to access/expand into new markets and experience an increased demand in their product/service portfolio. **Key messages** will focus on highlighting this potential, seeking to attract collaboration opportunities and partnerships for the provision of materials/manufacturing techniques for SSB. Relevant EU actors outside the consortium to be targeted include BASF, UMICORE, IBUtec and Northvolt, ACC, FAAM, Basquevolt among others.

Battery manufacturers and developers among OEMs: SAFT, as SOLVE's main battery manufacturer, stands to gain substantial benefits from the insights generated in the production of SSB. **Key messages** will emphasize the idea of enhanced international market competitiveness and differentiation for SAFT and its associated partnerships (i.e., ACC, AB Members).

System integrators and end-users: Automotive OEMs, represented in the consortium by CRF, will be the main target. OEMs for other mobility applications such as aviation and aerospace will also be considered, represented in SOLVE by PVS. **Key messages** will focus on showcasing these players the enhanced battery performance achieved to attract them to establish potential partnerships and integrate SSB technology into their products. EU automotive players aiming to get into the market with SSB-powered EVs include BMW, Mercedes-Benz AG, FCA Group, PSA Group, Renault and Volkswagen group.

Battery sectoral and cross-sectoral associations: Associations, such as Batteries Europe, European Battery Alliance, Battery 2030+, LiPLANET, UPCELL; BEPA and BATT4EU etc., serve as crucial gateways to national and European industrial ecosystems within the battery industry and to establish important links for the exploitation and dissemination of the project's innovations. **Key messages** will emphasize the project's significance and relevance to the sector, highlighting how it contributes to the industry's growth and competitiveness. The aim will be to seek close collaboration with these associations and leverage the project's network.

Investors: Verified industrial transferability findings, covering economic and environmental aspects, will help attract private investments for consortium's technology developers from VC firms, angel investors and other sources. **Key messages** aimed at investors will emphasize the project's potential for driving innovation within a rapidly expanding sector, its capacity for market disruption, the competitive advantage it offers, and the potential for attractive financial returns.

Standardization bodies and policy makers: SOLVE products are being developed to reach the objectives defined by the SET plan in terms of performance, reliability, sustainability and environmental footprint, in line with the expectations of Directive 2006/66/EC and the new Battery Regulation. **Key messages** will focus on interaction with these stakeholders to validate the compliance of SOLVE products with the current and the future EU regulatory framework, and to implement bilateral feedback.

Society at large: Any individual, association or business with interest in the electric mobility. **Key messages** will highlight the project's societal, environmental and economic impacts, seeking to foster partnerships to drive awareness, education and support. Diverse communication channels will be utilized to effectively reach non-specialized audiences.

1.4. IDENTIFICATION OF THE TARGET GROUP

A mapping exercise has been done in order to identify the key stakeholders of the SSB value chain in Europe, led by TEN with the support of CID and inputs of the whole consortium. The complete mapping is available to the SOLVE partners in the Share Point and its results will be shared with the community through the project website and social media posts.

In the mapping, made on an Excel file, there are five tabs:

————— In the first one “Initiatives and EU Networks”: there is a list of the EU networks and alliances in the sector of Solid-State Batteries. Most of the project partners are already members of those initiatives and they are good entry points for project results dissemination, to organize common events and to explore exploitation options.

————— The second tab entitled “Projects” lists the EU-funded projects focused on the SSB development. They are mostly Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects. Overall, 26 projects have been identified in the last six years. This work was useful to identify the key actors of the SSB sector.

————— The third tab, “List of actors Europe” lists all the partners in the EU projects identified in the previous tab. They are also classified by typology (University, Industry, Research Center, SME, and other) as well as their position on the value chain (raw materials and active materials providers, component and cell manufacturers, batteries integrators and end users, second life and recycling, consultancy). Their affiliation to any network identified in tab 1 has also been listed.

————— The fourth tab “Summary actors Europe” is a summary of the previous slide, mainly in order to show the relevance of each actor. The “Impact” column is calculated on the number of projects they are partners in and the number of projects they are leading. It was decided to factor that being partner in a project counted as 1 and being a lead partner (coordinator) in a project counted as 2. It is based on these numbers that map and value chains figures will be prepared.

————— The last tab “other actors”, aims to identify other actors, based in the EU or not which are working in the SSB value chain.

Name	Country	Number of Projects	Among which Lead ?	Impact	Typology	Value chain	Value chain 2
CEA	France	11	1	12	Research Center		
Umicore SA	Belgium	12	0	12	Industry	Raw manufacturing and Active Material Providers	
ABEE	Belgium	8	3	11	Industry	Module and Pack manufacturing	
CICenergiGUNE	Spain	9	2	11	Research Center		
Fraunhofer	Germany	10	0	10	Research Center		
Technische Universitaet Braunschweig	Germany	9	0	9	University		
Uppsala Universitet	Sweden	7	1	8	University		
CNRS	France	6	1	7	Research Center		
AIT	Austria	5	1	6	Research Center		
Toyota Motor Europe	Belgium	6	0	6	Industry	Battery Integration and End Users	
UniAcademia BV	Netherlands	6	0	6	University		
VTT	Finland	4	2	6	Research Center		
Centro Ricerche FIAT	Italy	5	0	5	Industry	Batteries integrators and end users	
CIDETEC	Spain	4	1	5	Research Center		
Leitat	Spain	3	2	5	Research Center		
PULSEDEON OY	Finland	5	0	5	SME	Components and cell manufacturing	
Universitaet Muenster	Germany	5	0	5	University		
ACCUREC Recycling GMBH	Germany	4	0	4	Industry	Second life and recycling	
Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas	Spain	3	1	4	Research Center		
FEV Europe GMBH	Germany	3	1	4	Research Center		
IKERLAN	Spain	4	0	4	Research Center		
INEGI	Portugal	4	0	4	Research Center		
Politecnico di Torino	Italy	4	0	4	University		
SAFT	France	4	0	4	Industry	Components and cell manufacturing	
TNO	Netherlands	4	0	4	Research Center		
UL	Slovenia	4	0	4	University		
Varta Microbattery	Germany	4	0	4	Industry	Module and Pack manufacturing	
VDL Enabling Transport Solutions BV	Netherlands	4	0	4	SME	Battery Integration and End Users	
VUB	Belgium	4	0	4	University		

Figure 1: Extract of the Excel mapping.

The data collected will be updated throughout the project to stay relevant and to be able to identify new actors and any news concerning the value chain.

This mapping is part of T7.1 and T7.2 as the necessary basis for dissemination and communication as well as the collaboration with EU initiatives and projects including stakeholder engagement. It will also allow the partnership to elaborate a precise SSB value chain of the EU actors.

The next steps are to identify collectively the most relevant actors with whom elaborate dissemination activities during the project's lifetime and to organize events to gather inputs from experts on SOLVE's results. Then to organize those activities.

Figure 2: Number of actors identified along the SSB value chain.

Participants in HEU SSB projects

Figure 3: Map of the EU, based on the impact of participants in HEU SSB projects.

1.5. COMMUNICATION STYLE

To provide communication that will reach the targets mentioned above, it was decided to use a consensual style of communication. This decision implied a global analysis in terms of colours, shapes and graphic inspirations.

The chosen style is minimalistic, highlighting the project's themes and characteristics, and using a range of colours with a pop connotation for modernity, while remaining light and sober on the graphic elements with institutional communication while maintaining a strong graphic bias. The wide range of colours avoids redundancy.

Finally, the graphic identity and the whole SOLVE environment around it must include original elements to stand out in a world saturated by logos and graphic elements that often borrow the same codes.

As far as the message is concerned, it is essential to maintain a serious tone, typical of scientific communication, but this does not prevent the use of original and even amusing tools to stand out from the crowd. In this style of project, however, offbeat communication is out of the question.

2. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

2.1. REMINDER OF EXPECTATIONS

Communication activity	Target audience(s)	KPI
Visual identity	All stakeholders	
The visual identity of the project (logo and brand for all materials) will be designed and created at the beginning of the project. (Ready by M3).		
Website	All stakeholders	1000+ visits/year
A dedicated website, providing both public and private accesses, will serve as a focal point for all the D&C activities. It will provide general information on the project scope and objectives. It will also grant public access to project's documents, and to the dissemination activities agenda (seminars, meetings and conferences). The website, ready by M3, will be maintained during 3 years after the project end to support the project's impact.		
Social networks	All stakeholders	+ 150 followers/year, +600 interactions/year
Professional and public social networks will be set-up at the beginning of the project to maximize the visibility of the published project results, the participation of consortium members to major events and to promote project's organized events.		
Newsletters	All stakeholders	2 newsletter/year
Electronic newsletters containing project updates, news, interviews, and other project-related information will be created. These newsletters will be sent to stakeholders and partner networks as well as uploaded on the project website.		

Printed promotional materials	All stakeholders	Updated each year
Printed promotional materials, like flyers, leaflets, roll-ups, etc. will be formatted by TEN and distributed to project partners upon demand. Partners will be encouraged to ask for these materials and bring them into the different events.		
Videos	All stakeholders	2+ videos
Interviews with consortium members to present the project (M10) and main results (M36).		
Press releases	All stakeholders	1 press release/year
Electronic press releases containing project updates, news, interviews, and other project-related information will be created.		

2.2. VISUAL IDENTITY

2.2.1. THE LOGO

Figure 4: SOLVE logo evolution.

The SOLVE logo, as originally proposed for the application (opposite left), has been improved to give it more meaning and to tighten up the outline lines and the spacing between the letters and the outline of the battery.

The SOLVE logo is inspired by the shape of a battery, with the 'E' evoking the charge level of the battery. The logo is subject to certain rules of use to ensure that it is legible and recognizable. For more information, please refer to the deliverable: D7.1 "PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY, WEBSITE AND SOCIAL NETWORKS ACCOUNTS."

2.2.2. TYPOGRAPHY

Figure 5: Fractul typography.

The 'Fractul' master typography has been chosen to maintain sufficient originality to stand out from the crowd. The lines of this typeface give it a technical feel, with shapes reminiscent of electrical diagrams and lines close to the project's graphics. It will be used for corporate communication, particularly the website's window communication, but also on print communication tools. This typeface will only be used by the communication leader.

Figure 6: Arial typography.

The secondary typeface arial will be used for all content. This font is known for its simplicity and legibility and is the most appropriate for scientific and educational content. A pragmatic typeface that will be used by all members of the consortium. This font also has the advantage of being installed on all computers.

2.2.3. COLOURS

Figure 7: Charter colors.

A palette of colors has been defined for SOLVE's visual identity. This limited selection makes it easier to identify and remember the 'brand'. The combination of colors must always ensure good legibility: pastel colors contrast with the two main colors (blue and green), which are sharper. Blue recalls the color of Europe.

2.2.4. SHAPES

Figure 8: Charter shapes.

Shapes have been designed for the brand. They are inspired by electrical diagrams, to create a strong and meaningful group identity.

For more information on the project's communication identity, please refer to the deliverable: D7.1 "PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY, WEBSITE AND SOCIAL NETWORKS ACCOUNTS".

2.3. WEBSITE

As explained above, the website should be the showcase for the project. It will be updated as the project progresses. Each member of the consortium can contribute to its content by publishing scientific articles and research results from the project. Visitors can contact the project leaders using a contact form. A contact address: contact@solveproject.eu has been created to receive these requests. CID as coordinator and TEN as communication leader are responsible for collecting requests.

In order to be able to benefit from a great deal of latitude in the production of content, it has been agreed with the communications agency that almost all of the content on the site can be modified directly within the project by TEN.

Some illustrations of the website interface are shown below. For a more detailed presentation of the website, please refer to the deliverable D7.1 "PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY, WEBSITE AND SOCIAL NETWORKS ACCOUNTS".

Figure 9: SOLVE website – screenshot of homepage.

Figure 10: SOLVE website - Project challenges explained for each stage of the value chain.

Figure 11: SOLVE website – The members of the consortium are presented with links to their websites.

Figure 12: A contact form allows visitors to contact us, send comments and/or ask questions about the project.

2.4. SOCIAL NETWORKS

2.4.1. LINKEDIN

The LinkedIn account of the SOLVE project must communicate the progress of the project intended for an expert, scientific and professional audience. Scientific publications as well as specific dissemination and communication events linked to the project, including updates on project development and project meetings, can, in particular, be relayed there. LinkedIn is a network that highlights expertise and content intended to provide information that can be useful and fuel the debate on ideas. Interactions will be very important and outside ideas welcome.

The tone must remain serious, even if it is possible to offer slightly offbeat content to perform.

LinkedIn campaigns will be planned throughout the project, enabling the consortium members to be introduced in the first year, and then in next years to communicate results, news and events. Publications will be advertised in the most favorable time slots, i.e. Tuesdays and Thursdays around midday.

As a communications leader, TEN has set itself a target of between 20 and 30 posts per year and to try to capture an interaction of 10+ reactions per post. CID will review the posts before publication to ensure the quality and scientific accuracy of the content.

Figure 13: Examples of posts for the campaign (here CIDETEC Energy Storage team – left, and Arkema team - right).

2.4.2. X

The X page will make it possible to address the media world (journalists) and public authorities, who could act as powerful relays for the project. The publications will be rarer than on LinkedIn, but we will highlight the most important information, the major progress of the project illustrated by press releases, likely to interest the media. Up to now, the X account has mainly been used to relay news of interest to the press or influencers. Below is the press release announcing the launch of the project:

As a communications leader, TEN has set itself a target of 10 posts per year, trying to capture an interaction of 3+ reactions per post.

Figure 14: Example of post on X.

2.4.3. YOUTUBE

The YouTube page should serve as a support for other networks. Presentation of videos from the consortium partners and more technical interviews on the progress of the project will be published there. The videos may be published in an offbeat tone or not. To increase the performance of posts on social networks, it is strongly recommended to use fairly short video formats (2 min max) in order to keep the audience captivated by videos until the end.

The YouTube shorts model (10-30 seconds long videos in portrait mobile screen format) can also be used to boost performance.

As a communications leader, TEN has set itself a target of 5 videos per year and will try to capture an interaction of 30 views per video.

Figure 15: The YouTube page (screenshot).

2.5. NEWSLETTER

The plan is to produce a newsletter every six months, which will include the latest project news and results, as well as an announcement of upcoming events. Each member of the consortium will be asked to provide content relevant to its activities. The first newsletter is scheduled in February 2025.

The target will be fed by newsletter subscriptions that can be made from the website. This newsletter can then be relayed by the various members of the consortium to their internal targets.

Subscription to the newsletter will be recommended wherever the project is presented, to encourage people to follow the project in detail. Newsletter statistics will be closely monitored in order to adjust the target audience and newsletter content in real time.

This is the proposed structure of the newsletter:

PROJECT NEWS

- General Assembly
- Deliverables
- Publications
- Events where partners participated
- Social networks (published videos, invitation to follow)
- Future project events
- Where you will be able to find us in the next months: future participations in events

TECHNICAL PERSPECTIVE

- Short introduction about the authors and their institute
- Perspective from one partner about a technical part of the project
 - Suggested topics: SSB, solid electrolyte, cathode, anode, modelling, recycling etc.

OTHER SSB NEWS

- Big announcements of stakeholders
- Upcoming events: conferences, forums, webinars of interest
- Public funding opportunities
- Collaboration opportunities

2.6. PRINTED PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

Several tools will be in production by autumn 2024. These materials will be used to promote the project at face-to-face meetings (trade fairs, events, workshops). Above all, they must be eye-catching and powerful. Only communication tools will be produced in the first year, with dissemination tools to follow once the initial results have been disseminated.

2.6.1. L-BANNER

Figure 16: Roll-up content.

For the purposes of the project, it was agreed to choose a tool that could combine efficiency and flexibility. The idea is to produce 3 L-banners (double-sided roll-ups). This means that when they are placed side by side, the surface area is large enough to provide a background for interviews. Initially, only the three rectos will be produced to create this background, and it is planned to produce the versos later in the project, which will be used to disseminate the results as the project progresses. There will be one side for communication and one side for dissemination.

Finally, each of these three roll-ups is designed to be used independently without compromising the message of the project.

2.6.2. FLYERS

Figure 17: Flyer design.

The plan is to produce a 3-part leaflet outlining the project. To make this tool more effective, the idea is to present it standing-up and partially folded. The leaflet has been designed with a drawing of a battery to attract even more attention.

2.6.3. GOODIES

Several ideas for goodies were put forward. There are plans for stickers or magnets with the SOLVE logo, which could be stuck on various materials. Water bottles with a battery design are also being produced.

These goodies can be for private use (between members of the consortium) or public use (distributed to an external target) depending on their nature.

2.7. PRESS RELEASES

To date, a press release has been sent out in English and in the respective languages of the consortium members in mid-June following the launch of the project. An article was published in the Dauphiné Libéré on 25 June for France following this press release.

PRESS RELEASE

24/06/2024

SOLVE: A HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT TO DEVELOP THE SOLID-STATE BATTERY FOR THE MOBILITY OF THE FUTURE!

The Spanish research institute CIDETEC Energy Storage will lead a consortium of 16 partners under the Horizon Europe program to deploy Gen4b solid-state batteries for mobility applications on a large scale. A research project with high hopes, as competition from the Asian battery market grows ever stronger.

A consortium of 16 partners met on June 12 and 13 in Donostia - San Sebastian to launch the Horizon Europe project: SOLID-state battery development and production to dRIVE the future of electromobility (SOLVE).

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Liquid electrolyte-based lithium-ion batteries (LIB) are considered the most well-established technology for transport electrification and are likely to remain the preferred option in the coming years. However, it is projected that the improvements in this technology will gradually decelerate towards the end of the decade when they approach their theoretical energy density limits. Therefore, it is imperative to diversify the battery technology offer along with the materials used for its production to reinforce Europe's battery industrial backbone.

In this sense, solid-state batteries (SSB) with Li metal anode (LIM-SSB, Gen4b) are considered the next major milestone in the industry by policymakers and mobility original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) due to their enhanced intrinsic safety, durability, their potential to improve fast-charging capability and extending driving range through higher energy density.

SOLVE aims to overcome the obstacles to the large-scale deployment of Gen4b solid state batteries for mobility applications. Over the next 48 months, the project will be supported by a consortium of 16 stakeholders across the entire battery value chain, with a special focus on:

- Achieving high-performing, cost-effective and safe Gen4b solid state batteries (Li-metal and anode-free) with nominal capacity of 20 Ah.
- Developing advanced materials and cell components with improved electrochemical performance and enhanced safety.
- Demonstrating highly sustainable, circular manufacturing for the selected advanced materials at Gigafactory scale, in accordance with EU Battery Regulation.
- Reaching an improvement in safety at representative 10-20 Ah cell level and 0.25 kWh mini-module level suitable for mobility applications.
- Disseminating the obtained results and create training activities contributing to the EU Battery landscape.

The project will be led by 16 organizations (companies, universities, research institutes, associations) from 8 European countries: CIDETEC Energy Storage (ES), SAFT (FR), Arkema (FR), Centro ricerche Fiat (IT), Pipistrel (SI), CEA (FR), Pulsedion (FI), Accurec recycling (DE), Delfort (AT), Politecnico Di Torino (IT), Tampere korkeakoulu (FI), Fraunhofer IKTS (DE), EMPA (CH), Oerlikon (CH), Lomartov (ES), Tenerdis (FR)

Contact presse

Eloïde Chene +33 6 79 38 05 09 eloide.chene@tenerdis.fr
Quentin Morel +33 6 12 38 03 19 quentin.morel@tenerdis.fr

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Recherche

Mobilité : ce nouveau projet européen veut développer la batterie du futur

Porté par l'institut de recherche Cidetec, le projet européen "Solve" veut déployer à grande échelle des batteries à état solide Gen4b pour des applications de mobilité. Seize organismes sont engagés dans ce travail, dont Tenerdis, le pôle de compétitivité de la transition énergétique en AURA.

Le Dauphiné Libéré - 25 juin 2024 à 18:00 | mis à jour le 25 juin 2024 à 19:16 - Temps de lecture : 2 min

Le projet "Solve" a été lancé les 12 et 13 juin derniers à Donostia, en Espagne. Photo Solve

Figure 18: Article in the Dauphiné libéré.

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23/30

2.8. PLANIFICATION

Figure 19: Agenda for communication activities.

Funded by the European Union (Grant n°.101147094) Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority (CINEA) can be held responsible for them.

3. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

3.1. REMINDER OF EXPECTATIONS

Dissemination activity	Target audience(s)	KPI
Peer-reviewed scientific publications	Academia, industry research teams	At least 10 peer-reviewed papers
<p>Project partners are expected to submit at least 10 open access articles by the end of the project. Relevant high-impact journals where to publish these articles may include Nature Materials, Nature, Energy, Advanced Materials, Chemistry of Materials, Energy & Environmental Science, Journal of Power Sources, Electrochimica Acta, Journal of the Electrochemical Society, Batteries & Supercaps, among others. After the project, effects will continue to be assessed using citation-based metrics, targeting Field-Weighted Citation Impact of >1.</p>		
Workshops and webinars	Industry, Scientific community	At least 4 workshops/webinars organised
<p>CID and TEN will organize dedicated workshops and webinars within the project's general dissemination strategy (T7.1), as well as part of the specific capacity building activities (T7.5). Whenever possible, these events will serve as bi-directional channels to obtain external input from experts, encourage knowledge transfer and to recruit new end-users for supporting the project. At least, 4 events will be organized during the last 3 years of the project, targeting a minimum audience of 50 attendees each and including roundtables with AB members. The online and hybrid format will be favoured to maximize the impact.</p>		
Conferences and events	All stakeholders	Attend at least 8 conferences/year and present in at least 4/year
<p>Efforts will be made to establish links with other EU-funded projects related to the HORIZON-CL5-2023-D2-02-01 topic, as well as relevant ongoing or future projects in the context of the Batt4EU Partnership. Strong focus will be made to establish cooperation with ongoing projects funded under the calls HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-03, D2-01-05 and LC-BAT-1-2019, many of which involve active participation from SOLVE partners (see Section 1.2.3). Cooperation with other key initiatives such as BEPA, Batt4EU, BATTERY 2030+ and EBA250 will also be sought to expand the project's scope and impact. Furthermore, partners will attend and present at other international events, conferences, and trade fairs to disseminate the project's results, including but not limited to: Advanced Battery Power Conference, BATTERY 2030+ Annual Conference, EUROBAT Forum, Battery Show Europe, Battery & Electrification Summit, Internationals Lithium Battery meeting, The Electrochemical Society meeting, International Battery Association conference, International Symposium on Polymer Electrolytes, International Society of Electrochemistry meeting, etc.</p>		
Training activities	Industry, Scientific community	Organisation of 1 summer school

As part of T7.5, CID in cooperation with the rest the partners will coordinate the development of different training activities oriented to both students and workforce, including the preparation of e-learning resources, the arrangement of specific workshops and webinars as mentioned above and the organization of a 2–3-day summer school aimed at students and young professionals working in the SSB field. Cooperation with relevant training activities such as MESC+ and MSCA Innovative Training Networks such as DESTINY and POLYSTORAGE will be sought.

3.2. ACTIVITIES

In order to guarantee the most relevant dissemination actions, the members of the consortium will help to define them. This will be the subject of a workshop at the General Assembly (GA01) in Turin, where everyone will be able to put forward their ideas.

Dissemination actions will only be possible once the first results have been obtained, which are not expected until the 2nd year of the project.

Publications in scientific journals should report the results of active work packages. The choice of these journals will have to take into account the specificities of these research areas.

Publish >10 peer-reviewed scientific papers in high-impact (Q1, IF >4) open access journals; at least 5 post-project KER joint developments; at least 5 IP protected research outputs within the project; at least 4 confirmed expressions of interest from industry end-users for KER technology adoption/adaptation secured.

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- at the time of publication, an electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or a license with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the license may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND), and
- information is given via the repository about any research output, or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication. Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output, or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

Only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

The workshops and webinars will be co-piloted by TEN as communication leader for the logistical aspects (registration, platform settings) and the leader of the work package concerned for the content and running of the webinar.

The first workshops and webinars are scheduled to take place as soon as the first results are available, in principle, not before 2026.

Participation in conferences and events may be proposed by members if events in their respective countries seem relevant to them. They will then have to inform the communication leader and the coordinator. This could take the form of purchasing a stand to exhibit at or participating in the animation of a trade show or conference by presenting the project.

Simply going to a trade show to distribute flyers can also be considered, but more as a communication action than a dissemination action.

4. COMMUNICATION RULES

Since SOLVE is a transnational project, with 16 partners from 8 EU countries, communication activities will require input from all project partners, to ensure that the target audience and key messages are appropriate for their respective region and activities. The communication and dissemination activities are planned to allow maximum stakeholder input and the widest possible reach across the EU and beyond. The “waterfall effect” will be possible only through the continuous interaction between project partners and the direct target and the potential beneficiaries.

In order to maximize the impact of the external communication and to ensure it will reach its goals, a few rules must be set in place:

- Be coordinated: communication activities should be coordinated, by TEN as communication leader,
- Be timely – planned communication activities should be linked to key project milestones or activities,
- Ensure the information is accurate,
- Aim the appropriate target audience,
- Define and use key messages that are of interest to the target audience(s),

4.1. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES TRACKER

Project partner	Publishing date	Type of media: Newsletter, Newspaper, Internet portal, TV, radio, podcast,...	Name of media	Title in original language	Title in English	Website link (if available) Please supply a PDF version	Country where the activity was reported
TENERDIS	25/06/2024	Internet	Dauphiné Libéré	Mobilité : ce nouveau projet européen veut développer la batterie du futur	Mobility: this new European project aims to develop the battery of the future	https://www.ledauphine.com/economie/2024/06/25/mobilite-ce-nouveau-projet-europeen-veut-developper-la-batterie-du-futur	France

Figure 20: Communication activities tracker.

Two files are made available on the project's common server so that the communication and dissemination activities undertaken by the various members of the consortium can be traced.

It is essential that each member keeps this table up to date and relays each of its activities. A reminder will be sent out each quarter and particular care will be taken to ensure that the table is filled in correctly.

The project partners must always keep the communication leader informed of the dissemination activities undertaken. Communication actions can be envisaged to highlight these actions.

4.2. WEBSITE

Each member can contribute to the content of the website. During the project, members may be asked to contribute feature articles on specific subjects to feed the website and keep it up to date with progress on the project.

4.3. PRESS

As far as possible, consortium partners are expected to relay press releases issued by the communication leader TEN, at least in English, although translation into the partner's language would be preferable.

4.4. SOCIAL MEDIA

SOLVE project posts should be able to be re-shared at least by LinkedIn profiles of project members, and as far as possible by members' company pages.

4.5. COMMUNICATION TOOLS

Each member of the consortium will receive a little pack of flyers at the general meeting in Turin, which they can use as required. If more flyers are needed, it will then be necessary for each member to print them in their own country according to their needs. A digital file ready for printing will be made available.

The 3 roll-ups produced for the project will be displayed at the various general meetings. Other roll-ups may be produced if the need arises to take part in events. The communications leader should be informed in advance.

5. CONCLUSION

This document summarizes the SOLVE consortium's communication and dissemination objectives for the duration of the project. It will be updated regularly to guide future actions.

It serves as a support for consortium members to help them in their participation in communication and dissemination efforts. It also summarizes what is expected from them. It is one of the reference documents that will enable the project to evolve in the right direction and ensure that ongoing actions are thoroughly monitored and accomplished.

TEN, as communication leader, is at the disposal of each consortium member to provide answers to these needs. The communication leader has to be the guarantor of good communication thanks to his expertise. Each member can feel free to make proposals.

6. ANNEXES

1. LinkedIn page link: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/solveproject/?viewAsMember=true>
2. X page link: <https://x.com/SOLVEprojectEU>
3. YouTube page link: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdPaxiEAqJxENTQF6bVGAhg>
4. Website link: www.solveproject.eu